

APPLICATION OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO THE BLIND AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED

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Abstract. *In this article is described various beneficial strategies and techniques implementing at the lesson when you teach foreign languages to the blind and visually impaired students. Moreover, it is expressed different types of games which you can apply as an interactive methods in teaching disabilities.*

Keywords: *self-realization, diagnostic, disabilities, dialectic, capacity, interethnic, competitiveness, verbalization, emotional.*

Changes in the character of education at the turn of the century - its emphasis, goals, and content - are increasingly directed toward "free human development," creative initiative, student freedom, competitiveness, and future specialized mobility. The most essential social duty is to prepare the blind for life and to include them in industrial relations. Obtaining an education for children with disabilities is one of the most important and necessary requirements for their successful socialization, full involvement in society, and effective self-realization in various forms of professional and social activities. In this regard, one of the most significant objectives of state policy in the field is to ensure the implementation of children with disabilities' right to education. When the lesson model is: "I know, but not everything; I would like to know - I found out," and the presence of problems or problematic learning tasks is assumed, research technologies necessitate the implementation of a pedagogical model - "learning through discovery," experimentation or modeling critical circumstances and discovering solutions to solve them, as well as gaming technology. Various learning technologies are employed for this purpose, each with its unique set of qualities and organizational structure.

When training is based on the active interaction of all participants in the educational process with the involvement of various media, and communication is the dominant approach, communication technologies have long been included in the methodology of teaching a foreign language. There are already a plethora of categories in the methodological literature that systematize the many types of educational games based on one or more classification criteria. Depending on the goals and objectives; forms of conduct; organization method; degree of difficulty;

and number of participants [O.Gazman,1991]. Gaming activity is very important in the practice of human relations and serves the following purposes:

- communicative: understanding the dialectic of communication;
- entertaining (the game's primary goal is to entertain, give pleasure, inspire, and arouse curiosity);
- therapeutic: conquering numerous challenges occurring in other forms of life;
- self-realization in the game as a basis for human behavior;
- diagnostic function: detecting departures from normal behavior, self-awareness throughout the game;
- correction function: modifying the structure of personal indicators in a good way;
- socialization: incorporation in the system of social connections, assimilation of human society's standards [G.Selevko,1998].
- interethnic communication: assimilation of universal social and cultural values.

As a result, games in the educational process have a lot of potential for improving the educational process for teaching foreign languages by creating and activating students' creative mental and cognitive capacities. Because the acquisition of new knowledge through the game coincides with their consolidation, multiple repetition does not "get boring," painlessly leading to a stronger assimilation, this activity activates students' cognitive abilities. During its implementation, the motivation to learn increases, the level of interest increases (heuristic function), skills and abilities are developed and improved (teaching function), because the acquisition of new knowledge through the game coincides with their consolidation, multiple repetition does not "get boring," painlessly leading to a stronger assimilation. Because the youngster does not perceive himself as an object of adult control in the game, but rather as a full-fledged topic of activity, it is feasible to shape his own attributes through the game (educational function). Students actively interact with one another, mastering the rules and methods of the process and gaining experience of mutual understanding, coordination of actions and intentions with other players. Participants learn to restrain their immediate desires for the sake of joint action (communicative function) by following the rules. It is easier to establish a culture of human values perception through the game (aesthetic function).

Blind children, like those who can see, want to be a part of group activities, but due to a less mobile lifestyle and a lack of personal experience, their activities differ greatly from those of regularly sighted children. "Speech develops essentially at the same time as well-seeing children" in blind children with normal intelligence development and the absence of organic lesions of the speech centers, because a substantial disability or lack of vision does not prevent the kid from speaking.

Although there are distinct characteristics in the development of a blind child's colloquial speech, this is mostly due to the uniqueness of mastering various types of speech activity.

The field of teaching a foreign language to the blind is understudied. Due to a lack of theoretical material, it is a dilemma for the teacher and stimulates his creative capacity. "Any ideas for special education for blind students within the framework of the school curriculum in individual institutions evoke fears of segregation," according to one of the reasons for the lack of research. Another factor impeding research in the aforementioned field is the widespread belief that blind persons are incapable of learning a foreign language. There are "professionals who doubt blind children's ability to learn a foreign language on par with sighted children" [T.Nikolic, 1987]. When adopting a strategy, the teacher must consider the children's qualities and limits, as well as the fact that their motivation is dependent on "communicative competence." The communicative method allows for a more expansive view. It considers not only the structural, but also the functional features of the language. However, there is another aspect of this method that is often overlooked but is critical to success: language has a social as well as a functional value.

Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are four abilities that should be taught to both blind and sighted children. The teacher should give students with a variety of English-language materials. They should be used in individual work as well as in the classroom.

1. **Speaking.** The adoption of particular phonetics and accents is the initial stage of conversation. It's crucial to explain sounds that don't exist in the local tongue. Because "it builds the foundations on which effective reading skills are created," the oral stage should be slightly broadened and merged "with text work." The teacher will have to deal with verbalization at a later point in the discourse.

2. **Reading.** Braille is a slower medium for reading. This fact is overlooked by the inexperienced teacher, who tries to aid and correct the learner far too soon. For blind persons who do not read with both hands, choosing the correct form of the definite article can be difficult since they cannot detect the word after it in advance. In the early stages of learning to read, the teacher should not expect outstanding results.

3. **Writing.** Learning new characters in the foreign language Braille is related with the beginning of learning to write, followed by the so-called double characters, which have one meaning in the native language and a separate meaning in the foreign. Although Braille is a global code, each language has its own unique features. They

have the potential to become a persistent source of errors. Before moving on to punctuation rules, this step requires extra attention.

4. **Listening.** In a foreign language education, good listening skills are quite beneficial. Unfamiliar sounds, speech, rhythm, and intonation of the language under study, on the other hand, present new opportunities for enhancing "listening" skills [A.Best, 1992]. Many factors influence successful English learning, however there are a few key roadblocks to overcome: - The visual obstacle's commencement and timing. - The degree to which a person's orientation and mobility conceptions have matured. - The level of Braille reading and writing ability. - The ability to express oneself verbally. - Comprehension of supporting maps and graphs.

Using contemporary technologies, such as electronic dictionaries, is a good method to handle some challenges. However, the instructor must still rely on his intuition and creativity. For blind students, the usage of a customized dictionary is critical, as the instructor cannot be the sole consistent supplier of new words. Braille dictionaries are still unavailable in some regions. There are three main approaches of teaching new words: 1) visual (display what you're talking about); 2) descriptive; and 3) "sound visuals." The majority of modern language courses rely heavily on visual representations of vocabulary.

The acoustic representation of new words is still in its infancy. However, sound recordings make many words simpler to convey: noises, an airplane, a railway, a horse, children splashing in water, gurgling, and so forth. We must remember that a blind person's environment is made up of "sound pictures," and he detects sounds far more clearly than a sighted person. When teaching blind youngsters, a visual manner of presenting new words is impossible. It is, however, vital to familiarize them with the surroundings. Depending on the theme of the class, the teacher may bring a variety of things, clothing, and toys. Students pass them on to one another, emphasizing key points.

The teacher makes use of 3D items whenever possible. Three balls of various sizes and materials, for example, can be used to learn the following concepts: 1. a ball (ball); 2. round shape (round shape); 3. hard and soft (hard and soft); 4. smooth and rough (smooth and rough); 5. heavy and light (heavy and light); 6. comparatives and superlatives: big, bigger, the biggest (comparative forms); 7. left and right (right, left); 8. prepositions of location: in front of, behind, between, under (prepositions of place). However, you must educate the pupil about the object before delivering it to him. A walk is another opportunity to expand your vocabulary by studying the environment around you. They can learn words like a tree, a bench, and a chair here.

To express the meaning of the phrase, the teacher must employ gestures and actions. It must, however, be combined with sounds. In some circumstances, the sounds are natural, and the teacher only needs to accentuate them. Physical touch is possible in the explanation of several words, such as pinch, pat, and squeeze. It's worth remembering that blind persons who are used to regular physical contact value it greatly. It is vital to employ not only the kinesthetic, but also the olfactory and gustatory systems when becoming acquainted with the outside environment. The study of food, and later the names of foods, is a good example of the application of taste and smell. Taste, on the other hand, can be useful in the study of colors. Many blind persons are familiar with the colors of fruits, vegetables, chocolate, and other foods. For children, lessons on items and colors become a true source of pleasure. The teacher should begin explaining concepts as soon as feasible so that students learn to deduce a word's meaning from its explanation. It is important to note that the blind rely solely on the teacher's explanations. The learner must provide feedback in the form of a paraphrase of one or more definitions. The use of numerous games targeted at teaching various components of a foreign language to visually impaired children is another approach of teaching a foreign language to them, which answers a variety of emotional, psychological, and didactic problems.

For instance, games targeted at teaching descriptive vocabulary in a foreign language when the key adjectives are introduced and developed according to established methods. With visually handicapped youngsters, all other potential techniques of introducing new lexical units are used, including tactile sensations, taste, smell, and explanation. Frontal and individual phonetic assessment are conducted after the presentation of a lexical unit (that is, when the teacher is confident that all students comprehend its meaning). Participants are placed in the following circumstances after learning the primary adjectives that help describe objects in the general frontal mode: they must describe the object, recognize it, talk about its use, and so on. The first step is to feel the object with your hands.

Task 1: Touch and describe these items. It's crucial to employ the speaker's taste and smell experiences in the next assignment. Any fruit must be tasted by the blind participant without touching it. The goal is to describe the flavor, name the fruit, and tell as much about it as possible.

Task 2: One of your communities' members will visit us. This person will be able to taste something without being able to see it. He or she will be required to describe the situation. You must talk about everything you imagine, not just the taste. The next job is to figure out what the learner is touching. It should specify the size, shape, and surface of the object.

To sum up, the instructor promotes the cognitive activity of blind children by teaching them to play and managing their creative games, allowing them to overcome developmental limitations caused by blindness. When working with a blind youngster, games should be based on sound and motor imitation, natural curiosity, orienting activity, a sense of delight from action that is as great in a blind person as it is in a seer, and a natural desire to move. and activities, which are sometimes overshadowed by apprehension about unknown objects.

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